

The Impact of Inflation on Household Consumption Patterns in Developing Economies

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ABSTRACT

The major area of this study is exploring how inflation shapes household consumption in developing economies. In this study, secondary qualitative data from recent reports and research are used. The study sheds light on how rising prices shape spending habits, especially for low-income families who spend the maximum percentage of their income on food and energy. The study also encompasses a content analysis approach, which establishes a comprehensive understanding of major issues, including reduced spending on health education, as well as coping strategies like borrowing or skipping meals, and the emotional stress caused by inflation. The outcomes show that inflation worsens poverty and inequality, which calls for targeted support to protect vulnerable households from inflation shocks.

Keywords: Inflation, household consumption, developing economies, content analysis, coping strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

The continuous increase in the general price level of goods and services is defined as Inflation. The term "inflation" has various meanings in various contexts. It is the thought of many economists that inflation is the outcome of an increase in the amount of money relative to the supply of available goods. In the global scenario, inflation primarily affects the overall purchasing power of people by increasing the cost of goods and services and decreasing their buying capacities. High inflation is universally considered harmful, but some economists still state that a small amount of inflation can have a huge impact on driving economic growth (Krugman 2014). Inflation is theoretically supported by increased production only

if the economy is not running at capacity, which means there is unused labour or resources.

On the other hand, when the subject comes to household consumption, inflation has the most profound impact. During inflationary situations, essential items such as food, fuel, and utilities become highly expensive, so that it is tough for households to spend on non-essential goods or services like education, healthcare, and clothing (Maina 2017). In turn, the reallocation of consumption hampered the overall well-being of individuals as well as affected long-term development goals, including health and literacy outcomes.

Aim of the study

In this study the main purpose is exploration of how household consumption patterns in developing economies are impacted by inflation.

Research objectives

- To examine how inflation affects household spending priorities in developing economies.
- To identify common coping strategies adopted by households during inflationary periods.
- To analyse existing qualitative data from reports and case studies using content analysis.
- To explore the broader social and economic implications of changing consumption patterns.
- To provide insights that can inform policy responses targeting inflation-affected households.

Research Question

- How does inflation influence household consumption behaviors in developing economies?

2. Literature Review

There are a huge number of studies that delve into how inflation impacts household consumption,

especially in the context of developing economies. Studies have mentioned that in developing economies, a sudden fluctuation in the overall price graph initially hampers the regular expenditure scenario of people. A study by Piereson, (2012) highlights the perspective of renowned British economist John Maynard Keynes in relation to inflation and its deep impact on the economy. According to Keynes, some inflation was necessary to prevent the Paradox of Thrift. Here, the paradox of thrift is used for being an economic theory that places an argument on the fact that personal

savings are probably detrimental to overall economic growth. Another study by Jacobs et al. (2014) mentioned that inflation trlevelormed spending decisions of households entirely, it happens particularly when the graph of incomes stays at the same line, but the cost of living increases rapidly. Severe inflationary periods mostly hamper the overall lifestyle of low-income households, this is because such people usually invest the maximum percentage of their income on items that are necessary in daily life, such as food and utilities (Mwanzia 2014).

Figure 1: Price Changes in Selected Categories (Feb. 2012 - Feb. 2014) and Their Impact on the Poor
(Source: Bencasselman 2014)

On the other hand, as mentioned in a few studies that inflation triggers a reprioritisation of spending, which means it pushes households to transform the order of importance into how they spend their money. A study by Winkelried and Gutierrez (2015), mentioned that in Peru and Indonesia, during the time of high inflation, a sharp decline is seen in the expenditure graph of several low-income families, specifically in healthcare, education, and clothing. One thing that families continued to spend the same or even more on, even after high inflation, is food expenses. It represents whether high-income households or low-income households investing in food remains the same in the regular budget. A study by Waxman (2012), found that inflation increases the consumption of cheaper food alternatives among low-income households, which in turn creates a lack of nutritional intake among them, especially in children and women. Besides these areas, some studies also emphasise coping mechanisms against inflation. As reported especially in developing countries, many households still use coping strategies, such as borrowing from informal networks, reducing meal frequency, and withdrawing children from school during inflation (Nadu 2015). Apart from the economic implications, inflation also deeply affects the psychological and emotional aspects of families. Persistent inflation sometimes led to anxiety, family stress, and reduced social engagement. When the subject comes to the pressure of inflation in households in developing economies, it is seen that rapidly increasing prices of food erode their limited purchasing power. A study by the Asian Development Bank shed light on the fact that a small increase in staple food prices across developing Asia could make the ratio of poverty extreme (Gillson and Fouad 2014).

Figure 2: Share of Global Poverty by Income Level of Countries, 1990 vs. 2012
(Source: GSDRC 2016)

India is one of the developing countries; therefore, in India still at the time of high inflation, low-income households spend more than their income on food just to maintain their dietary intake (Varadharajan et al. 2013). Another example is Bangladesh, where female-headed households already allocate a significant part of their income to food (Mallick and Rafi 2010). Such information sheds light on the fact that the disproportionate burden of food inflation on already vulnerable households not only intensifies poverty but also undermines nutrition and sets boundaries in access to education and healthcare. As seen in different studies, the after-effects of inflation have significant direct as well as indirect implications for household consumption in developing economies. Studies have shed light on the fact that apart from putting pressure on the income graph of a person, such effects sometimes create extreme pressure on the social and psychological well-being of a person.

The scenario of Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, and Latin America reflects that inflation initially had an impact on real purchasing power by reducing it. Inflation is really a nightmare for those households that already spend the maximum amount of their income on food (Romani, 2012). A rapid increase in food prices sometimes makes the situation extremely tough for low-income families to maintain their regular consumption levels. As Food is a basic need to survive, therefore, it has been in one and only choice for families to shift their spending away from other important sectors such as education, healthcare, and transport. In further dynamics, the shift in spending priorities poses very crucial consequences on human development indicators like nutrition, school attendance, as well as overall health.

As mentioned in a study by Ivanic et al. (2011), the World Bank ensures that household welfare can be significantly reduced with even a moderate inflation spike. A common consequence of inflation that is seen in many developing countries is, reduction in food consumption and setting limitations on daily meals. Children are most crucially affected because of these effects, and sometimes they are attacked with malnutrition. The initial consequence of inflation is harsh on the physical and mental development of children (van Vonderen et al. 2014). During inflationary periods, to manage a daily expense, households adopt a range of coping strategies, starting from cutting back on meals, pulling children out of school, to delaying essential healthcare. It is true that these decisions give a temporary relief to households but may bring long-term consequences. The mental and emotional effects of inflation are also significant. Unfortunately, long-term economic strain causes not only financial downturns but also brings several mental issues like stress and anxiety levels, especially among those responsible for managing household expenses. In this scenario, gender brought up another layer of

complexity. There are some regions where female-headed households are most of the time experience food insecurity (Dunga and Dunga 2017). It is because women bear more caregiving responsibilities compared to their earnings. In female-headed households, inflation leads to poor nutrition and health challenges for mothers, as women prioritise feeding their children over themselves.

Apart from this, geographic differences are also somehow responsible for influencing how inflation is felt. At the time of inflation, rural households experience severe complications because, sometimes due to inflation, transport costs are highly increased, and access to services like education and healthcare is limited. Economically weak households in rural areas are also affected by infrastructure-related issues, which make it tough for them to adapt to inflation (Sugema et al. 2010). The effects of inflation are also sometimes shaped by the employment structures. In developing countries, there are still a lot of families that depend on informal jobs, which do not provide regular income or job security. Such workers sometimes face stagnant earnings, even as living costs continue to rise. In turn, when essential goods become unaffordable due to inflation, they experience extreme pressure to manage daily necessities. Besides these challenges, in this context, government backup also played a vital role. Countries that have well-designed safety net programs, including targeted food subsidies or cash transfers, are able to protect vulnerable families. Though untargeted or poorly managed policies do not reach the needed ones as well as also sometimes bring additional strain on public resources.

The contribution of existing studies in establishing the understanding of how inflation influences household consumption in developing economies is commendable, but still as many of them emphasise measurable insights rather than explorable facts, there is a need for more exploration in this particular context. The limited qualitative exploration into the lived experiences of affected households, like how they perceive inflation, adjust their daily consumption, and emotionally respond to economic pressure, can make a huge gap in research. In this study, this gap is addressed by capturing the behavioural and psychological dimensions of household decision-making during inflationary periods in low-income contexts.

3. Methodology

A qualitative secondary research approach is best-suited in the context of this study. With this approach, the study can reach its initial aim, which is to explore how inflation affects household consumption patterns in developing economies. The study progressed with the analysis of already existing sources like academic journal articles, research papers, NGO field reports, and international organisation publications from the last five years, rather than involving the collection of new, measurable data (Goundar 2012). All of these sources are chosen in the context of this study because they give authentic, reliable and descriptive information in the subject of how families belong to developing countries experience and respond to rising prices. After the completion of data collection, the content analysis method is used for conducting a comprehensive analysis of the data. In the overall data analysis approach, common ideas, repeated themes, as well as patterns in household behaviour are identified (Ørngreen and Levinsen 2017). The major focus area of the study is how, in developing countries, households adjust their spending on essentials such as food, education, and healthcare, and how they cope at the times of severe inflation.

In the subject of selecting sources, only relevant, credible, and recently published (mostly between 2010 and 2017) sources are acknowledged. Documents that solely emphasise the impact of inflation in developing countries are included. The study also ensures that all sources are cited properly, and the data is interpreted without misrepresenting the original context.

4. Findings and Discussion

As highlighted in reports, the consequences of inflation in developing economies are very severe. Inflation led to a major shift in how families allocate their limited income (Flower and Wales 2014). A study by the World Bank sheds light on the fact that in low-income countries, the poorest 20% of the population invest around 60% of their income on food, in comparison to around 20% for the richest 20% (Ortiz and Cummins 2011). Poverty is one of the crucial consequences of inflation, because in such a context, people purchase fewer things with the same amount of money. Inflation brings significant changes to how households spend their money, as well as making the financial vulnerability of already struggling groups extreme. There are a lot of examples where it is seen that families have to cut expenses on non-essential but important services like healthcare, school fees, transport, and clothing. During inflation, prices of some particular goods and services are sharply increased, but

as incomes remain stagnant, it is tough for people to bear the same daily expenses (Cochrane 2011). To maintain daily and essential expenses, people adopt short-term coping mechanisms such as borrowing money, cutting down meals, as well as switching to cheaper and less nutritious foods.

As these adjustments are just a temporary solution against inflation, in the long run, they can cause extreme health issues such as malnutrition, especially among women and children. Besides this, as inflation is connected with financial burden, it sometimes affects the mental health of an individual initially. A person who is suffering from extreme financial strain due to a sudden increase in price can feel anxiety, frustration, and hopelessness (Van Hal 2015). In turn for the emotional toll, they have reduced social participation, which creates a strain in family relationships. When inflation hits rural areas, the situation can be even worse. It is because in rural locations lack of infrastructure and access to affordable markets are common problems. Another harsh outcome of inflation is seen in female-headed households. In such households, women tend to earn less and fulfil their children's needs before their own; such a situation makes their survival even tougher. So, it can be said that inflation, in developing countries, alters spending habits as well as making issues such as poverty and inequality more severe.

2017 Inflation Forecasts

- Ireland will have the lowest inflation rate (0.4%). The Baltics will record the highest inflation with Lithuania leading the pack (3.2%). Regarding the largest economies in the Eurozone, Spain will see the highest inflation (2.0%), followed by Germany (1.8%).

Figure 3: Eurozone Inflation Outlook and Monthly Trends, 2017

(Source: Focus Economics 2017)

The rise in food prices disproportionately affected the poor, because due to this, they have reduced their expenditure on healthcare, education, clothing, and transport. As seen in urban South Sudan, due to inflation, families are reducing non-food expenses and experiencing higher unemployment. Inflation not only increased food insecurity but also impacted energy costs by taking up 14% of income for low-income families, compared to 5.5% for higher-income groups.

The shift in spending behaviour ultimately reflects that inflation periods pushed households to spend only on survival needs, like food, rather than long-term investments in well-being, including education or healthcare. They have to do so because they have already spent a huge portion of their income on food and energy, and are not able to spend on other essential services, as after spending it on essentials, they are left with a small portion of the amount. As time goes by, the direct effects of inflation unfortunately affect children's education, family health, and even housing stability. After inflation, there are many households that have survived deeper poverty because they can no longer afford basic items.

Maximum time, the poorest households face the extreme side of inflation as they do not have savings or access to affordable credit. There are many regions in some developing countries where inflation even limits access to transportation. Such disadvantages make the regular life of a middle-class household even tougher. Apart from an increase in transportation costs, a small hike in energy prices also impacts many things, and most importantly, cooking, which affects both comfort and safety of a person in order to ensure regular survival. In such a type of situation, families have to choose between buying food and paying for medicine or school. The economic strain created by inflation also has a significant role in the creation of stress and emotional fatigue, particularly for female caregivers.

Figure 4: Inflation Rates Across Countries (1997-2012)

(Source: Jareño and Tolentino 2013)

As mentioned in the study of Umaru and Zubairu (2012), in an economy, inflation refers as a sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services. When the subject comes to developing economies, the impact of it is not similar for every group, as it is usually seen that low-income households are victims of extreme poverty, unemployment and inequality. For living a good life in an inflationary dynamic, there are a lot of households that adopt numerous short-term coping strategies. They have used savings, borrowing money, or selling assets as such strategies. Coping strategies provide temporary relief from the consequences of inflation, but such strategies do not ensure long-term financial security. The most severe outcome of repeatedly adopting such strategies is a decline in long-term household stability. After exhausting all the savings and selling assets, families do not have the scope to cope with future shocks. With the repeated use of coping strategies, families, though unintentionally, create a cycle of vulnerability, where each period of inflation forces households to dive into extreme poverty.

Another crucial thing related to coping strategy is high interest rates, which come with the borrowing strategy during inflation. It has extended future debt burdens. In the situation of extreme financial burden posed by the sudden hike in prices, families frequently cut back on important needs, such as food quality, health services, or education for children. In the long run, this led to poorer health outcomes, lower educational attainment, as well as reduced economic mobility. When the subject comes to female-headed households, the pressure is more significant because inflation makes women confused in choosing between caregiving responsibilities and managing financial stress. So, it has been clear that without sustainable growth in income and social support, coping strategies make the long-term impact of inflation even harder to overcome.

Years	Unemployed people(% of economically active population)	Inflation (%)
1999	13.0	36.6
2000	10.6	20.1
2001	8.9	18.8
2002	7.9	15.1
2003	8.2	12.0
2004	7.8	11.7
2005	7.1	10.9
2006	7.1	9.0
2007	6.0	11.9
2008	6.2	13.3
2009	8.3	8.8
2010	7.3	8.8
2011	6.5	6.1
2012	5.5	6.6
2013	5.5	6.5
2014	5.3	11.3
2015	5.8	11.2

Figure 5: Unemployment because of inflation (1999 to 2015)

(Source: Alisa 2015)

The impact of inflation is not even for every household. As seen in rural, older or low-income populations, the consequences of inflation are severe because these groups heavily rely on energy and have limited access to price controls (Naz et al. 2012). In Bangladesh, female-headed households are especially vulnerable to inflation because they have spent the maximum amount of their income on food. Such an imbalance in impact sheds light on the structural inequalities within developing economies. In rural areas, inflation crucially hits transportation and fuel costs, only because of long supply chains and poor infrastructure. There are a lot of older individuals who are entirely dependent on pensions, which is their fixed income, and do not adjust in line with rising prices. Inflation exposed such citizens to severe financial stress. On the other hand, female-headed households often deal with dual disadvantages, which are lower average earnings as well as higher caregiving responsibilities. During inflation, women as play the role of caregivers in this society, giving the first attention always to food and children's needs, and sometimes sacrificing their own nutrition and health. It causes long-term health issues as well as financial instability. There are many examples where it has been seen that these households are also excluded from formal financial services. Such inequality makes it is really hard to access credit or support during the rapid increase in the economic graph. Therefore, beyond targeted policy measures including food subsidies, energy assistance, or income support, the burden of inflation makes the overall well-being of the most marginalised populations more difficult. It also further makes poverty and inequality extreme across regions.

Figure 6: Inflation Trends for Different Income Groups

(Source: White 2014)

In reports, inflation is also acknowledged as an emotional breakdown, instead of only a financial burden (Cochrane 2011). Apart from the financial crisis, Inflation also brings up stress, anxiety, and uncertainty about the future, which worsens the mental state of a person. Food prices also have a major role in shaping expectations around inflation, which creates anxiety even when prices stabilize.

Figure 7: Impact of inflation on Mental Health

(Source: Self-developed)

Inflation can worsen poverty and inequality. It is proven by seeing that countries such as Nigeria and Zimbabwe experience worsening living standards only because of food price shocks and currency crises (Monnin 2014). To survive Inflation, developing countries need to integrate targeted interventions, including cash transfers, food aid, and energy subsidies. These initiatives also protect vulnerable households.

5. Conclusion

As seen in the entire study, the impact of inflation in household consumption patterns in developing economies is very significant. The study uses recent data and secondary qualitative sources to build a comprehensive understanding of how inflation alters the well-being of many households. It has been seen from the findings that inflation mostly affects low-income households, who have already spent most of their income on essential items such as food and energy. The study has clarified the fact that with the rise in prices, families are pushed to cut spending on healthcare, education, as well as other non-essential needs. There are also some short-term coping strategies like borrowing, reducing meals, or selling assets, which often give temporary relief from the harsh financial burden posed by inflation. The study also sheds light on the emotional consequences of inflation, such as fear and uncertainty or extreme anxiety about the future. So, as learned from the study, inflation exacerbates poverty, reduces well-being, and limits access to important services. These effects can be reduced by governments' support, like food assistance and cash transfers to help the most affected households during times of high inflation.

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